

ESTIMATION OF MERCURIC SALTS BY REDUCTION WITH SODIUM FORMATE

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A procedure is described for evaluating mercuric salts by reducing them to metallic mercury with a 40% solution of sodium formate. The precision is 1% or better. The method with a slight modification has been used for volumetric estimation by thiocyanate solution. Neutral or acidic solutions of various salts of mercury have been successfully analysed, except for mercuric cyanide which failed to be reduced. Analysis has also been carried out in presence of other metals, mainly silver and lead, which do not interfere.

Fuchs (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1929, 78, 125) determined neutral alkali formates by titration of the hydrochloric acid liberated during oxidation with mercuric chloride:

Fuchs titrated with alkali to the appearance of a yellow precipitate of mercuric oxide, but Oldeman (*Pharm. Weekblad*, 1931, 68, 379) made the procedure more precise by titrating the acid to phenolphthalein end-point, after tying up the excess mercuric chloride with sodium chloride. Present worker has further modified this procedure (this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 320) for microestimation of formate solutions containing one mg. of formic acid with a precision of 1%. All these facts reveal that this oxidation reaction is highly reproducible. Hence, it was felt that a reversal of this process could be used for the estimation of mercuric chloride as well. The present paper describes the determination of mercuric salts by reduction with sodium formate solution. It was noticed that on heating mercuric salts with a large excess of sodium formate for a long time, the reduction was not carried to the mercurous state only, but to metallic mercury.

EXPERIMENTAL

Mercuric chloride solutions were prepared by weighing chemically pure variety of the salt and dissolving it in water. Mercuric nitrate solution was obtained by dissolving pure mercury in concentrated nitric acid and diluting the solution with water after boiling off the oxides of nitrogen. Mercuric acetate solution was prepared by dissolving the salt in water and standardising it with ammonium thiocyanate solution (Scott, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", 1952, p. 581) after acidifying with nitric acid. Mercuric perchlorate solution was obtained by dissolving mercuric carbonate in excess of perchloric acid and standardising it with thiocyanate solution.

Evaluation of Mercuric Chloride Solution.—A neutral solution of mercuric chloride (5-20 c.c.) containing 0.2-0.5 g. of mercury was pipetted into a 150 c.c. pyrex conical flask and treated with a 25% sodium acetate solution (5 c.c.). The acetate solution was added to suppress the H^+ -ion concentration which tended to increase

during the course of the reaction and impeded its velocity. The air in the flask was driven out as far as possible by passing steam into it. The steam was only allowed to play over the solution. After quickly adding about 20 c.c. of a 40% sodium formate solution, the flask was closed with a rubber cork and heated by immersing its lower portion, containing the reaction mixture, in boiling water. Heating was continued for 3 to 5 hours till a perfect grey precipitate, frequently accompanied by small globules of mercury, was obtained. The white precipitate of calomel was sometimes found to stick to the walls of the flask and consequently it escaped the reducing action of the formate solution. In such cases, the flask was cooled, shaken well to incorporate the precipitate into the reaction mixture and then reheated. On completion of the reaction, which was indicated by the perfect grey colour of the precipitate and considerable diminution in its size, the flask was cooled and its contents filtered through a G4 sintered glass crucible. The heavy precipitate of mercury was transferred with the help of a jet of water from a collapsible plastic wash-bottle and washed thoroughly with water. The final washing was done with 20 c.c. of acetone followed by 10 c.c. of ether. The crucible was dried in the open for about an hour and then weighed. The amount of mercury, thus obtained from the assay of six different solutions of mercuric chloride, are recorded in Table I. The error (0.2-0.6%) being always on the lower side was probably due to slight volatilisation of mercury.

TABLE I

Heated for (hrs.)	...	3	3½	4	4	5	5
Hg	Found (mg.)	183.5	200.8	367.4	400.2	421.8	449.0
	Calc. (mg.)	184.6	201.2	369.2	402.0	423.2	450.6

Evaluation of other Salts of Mercury

(i). *Mercuric nitrate*.—A solution of the salt (2.5 c.c.) in dilute nitric acid was pipetted into a 150 c.c. pyrex conical flask. A 10% solution of potassium chloride (~5 c.c.) and a 15% sodium acetate solution (10 c.c.) were added, when a slight white precipitate was obtained. This precipitate did not interfere with the present procedure. After replacing the air in the flask by steam, a 40% solution of sodium formate (20 c.c.) was added in the manner already described. The reaction was completed by heating the stoppered flask for 4 to 5 hours in boiling water and the mercury obtained was washed and weighed.

(ii). *Solutions containing acetate, perchlorate, phosphate and iodide* (as K_2HgI_4) of mercury were all estimated by the above procedure and the results obtained are recorded in Table II. Neutral mercuric cyanide solutions, even on heating for a very long period with formate solution, failed to give any precipitate.

TABLE II

Evaluation of some mercuric compounds.

(Heated for 5 hours)

Mercuric compound.	Hg present.	% Mercury found by			
		Gravimetric.	% Error.	Volumetric	% Error.
1. Acetate	254 mg.	256 mg.	+0.8	255 mg	+0.4
2. Nitrate (in dil. HNO ₃)	457	454	-0.7	456	-0.4
3. Perchlorate (in dil. HClO ₄)	323	320	-1.0	320	-1.0
4. Phosphate (in dil. HCl)	182	180	-1.0	181	-0.5
5. Iodide (as K ₂ HgI ₄)	360	353	-2.0	354	-1.8
6. Cyanide (in water)	201		No action		

Volumetric Method involving Direct Thiocyanate Titration.—Instead of weighing the mercury obtained in all the experiments, mentioned in this paper, it was found that it could also be estimated volumetrically after dissolving it in hot concentrated nitric acid. The dissolution was brought about in the sintered crucible itself. The solution and the washings were collected and evaporated to about 20 c.c. and then titrated with 0.1*N* ammonium thiocyanate solution in presence of ferric alum (Scott, *loc. cit.*, p. 581). The concentration of the mercury solution is important, as very dilute solutions are found to yield low values. The results of estimations made by this procedure are shown in Table II (under volumetric).

The dissolution of mercury in nitric acid was found to be quick when the metal was in the state of a fine powder. This was achieved specially in mercuric chloride solutions by adding about half a gram of potassium perchlorate to the reaction mixture.

Interferences.—Iron, cadmium and bismuth were found to interfere as they formed precipitates when weakly acidic solutions were treated with excess of sodium formate. Zinc, aluminium, lead and silver did not interfere provided that the solutions were prepared in dilute hydrochloric acid (Zn and Al) or in dilute nitric acid (Pb and Ag). Mixtures of lead and mercuric nitrates were estimated by a process similar to that described in connection with mercuric nitrate solution, except for the addition of potassium chloride, which was avoided as it gave a precipitate of lead chloride. The reduction of mercuric nitrate was found to progress through mercurous nitrate to metallic mercury. Lead nitrate remained unreduced. The results obtained gravimetrically agreed with the thiocyanate method and the error did not exceed 1%.

Mixtures of mercuric and silver nitrates in dilute nitric acid, when heated with sodium acetate and excess of sodium formate for 5 hours in a closed flask, gave an amalgam of silver and mercury. The silver salt was also reduced, probably quantitatively, to metallic silver. The amalgam was filtered through a G₄ sintered crucible, well washed with water and finally with acetone. It was dried by leaving it overnight in the open. The dry precipitate was in the form of a grey spongy solid,

provided that the silver content was more than 20% of the mercury present. This solid being non-adhering was easily and completely transferred to a silica crucible and heated gently in a fume cupboard over a Bunsen flame until the weight became constant. The loss in weight which was due to volatilisation of mercury was recorded. The heating was regulated so as to prevent the melting of silver. This method gave excellent results with a precision of 0.5% which was better than that obtained for mercuric nitrate alone. The amalgamation of mercury with silver seemed to prevent its volatilisation, and hence, afforded better results.

D I S C U S S I O N

This reduction process has one disadvantage, that it requires prolonged heating for about 5 hours, otherwise a part of the mercury remains in the mercurous state. Apart from this it has several advantages, specially in the assay of mercuric chloride solutions. The direct titration of mercuric salts with thiocyanate solution has numerous drawbacks. Apart from the interference produced by several other metals, it is inapplicable in presence of chlorides, bromides and phosphates (Karaoglanov, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1943, 128, 405). It also gives unreliable results when the mercury solution is very dilute. The present procedure overcomes these difficulties by precipitating the metal which may be weighed as such or dissolved in nitric acid and then titrated accurately with thiocyanate solution. Moreover, it is also applicable in presence of silver and lead, which interfere with several methods available for mercury estimation.

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